

VASProcar: Python tools for DFT calculations

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Abstract

We present VASProcar, an open-source program written in the Python 3 programming language, aiming to provide an intuitive tool for post-processing the output files produced by DFT package called VASP, through an interactive user interface. The code extracts information and results from the VASP output raw files, such as CONTCAR, KPOINTS, OUTCAR, PROCAR, DOSCAR, LOCPOT, PARCHG, and vasprun.xml. VASProcar was designed to automate the analysis of DFT calculations, being capable of performing a wide range of tasks, including the plot 2D of the band structure, as well as the projection onto it of the atomic and orbital contributions, spin components (S_x | S_y | S_z), as well as the different blends that can arise from these projections. The code is also capable of generating a 3D plot of the dispersion of the states on a 2D plane or the visualization of energy isosurfaces over a 3D portion of the Brillouin zone. It allows for the calculation and visualization of both 2D and 3D Fermi surfaces, as well as the level curves of a given state, on which it is possible to project the spin texture and its components. Finally, it is also capable of plotting the density of states (DOS), including the DOS projected by atoms (l-DOS) and/or orbitals (p-DOS), as well as calculating the average value of the Charge Density, the Electrostatic Potential, and the Dielectric Function in the x | y | z directions of the crystal lattice. This article provides an overview of the program's structure and presents an illustrative example to demonstrate its capabilities in data analysis from VASP outputs. The program can be run on Linux, macOS, and Windows platforms. The executable versions of VASProcar and some examples are available in the repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6343960>.

Keywords: dft; vasp; condensed matter; band structure; electronic properties; Fermi-surface; spin texture; orbital projection; density of states; python.

PROGRAM SUMMARY

Program Title: VASProcar

CPC Library link to program files: (to be added by Technical Editor)

Developer's repository link: <https://pypi.org/project/vasprocar>

Code Ocean capsule: (to be added by Technical Editor)

Licensing provisions(please choose one): GNU General Public Licence 3.0

Programming language: Python 3

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1. Introduction

In recent decades, the Density Functional Theory (DFT) [1, 2] driven by the growth of high-performance computing, has consolidated itself as one of the most used computational methods for calculating the electronic, structural, magnetic, optical and topological characteristics of materials, generating a great advance in condensed matter physics, by allowing the development of new materials as well as the prediction of new properties, some of which have not yet been verified experimentally. Among the various DFT-based simulation codes, we can highlight VASP [3, 4, 5], Quantum Espresso [6, 7], SIESTA [8], ABINIT [9, 10] and WIEN2k [11].

In general, DFT packages require a post-processing step in order to extract the results obtained from the calculation in a readable format. However, there are some problems that make it difficult to analyze these results, highlighting the internal structure and the size of the output files, which depending on the complexity of the analyzed system can reach Gigabits in size, thus, data processing becomes slow, either by using too much processing or memory. In this case, it is desirable to have a code capable of intelligently analyzing large files, spending the least amount of time and computational resources, and extracting only essential information for the user. The ideal tool should still be able to provide a high-quality graphical representation of the quantities of interest, either in the form of vector files or in data files that can be correctly interpreted by graphics software. In this article, we present VASProcar, an open-source package written in the Python 3 programming language [12, 13, 14] that aims to provide an intuitive tool for the post-processing of the output files produced by the DFT VASP code, through an interactive user interface.

VASProcar was designed to automate the analysis of DFT calculations regardless of the parameters used, such as the inclusion or not of spin-orbit coupling (SOC), spin polarization, collinear or non-collinear type calculations, including the different combinations of these parameters, which modify the internal structure of the output files. For a given calculation it is able to perform a wide range of tasks, including the plot of the band structure, as well as the projection onto it of the atomic, orbital, and Spin components contributions as well as the different mixtures that may arise from such projections. The code is also capable of generating a 3D plot of the dispersion of states on a 2D plane, or the visualization of energy isosurfaces on a 3D portion of the Brillouin Zone. Allows the calculation and visualization of both 2D and 3D Fermi surfaces, as well as the level curves of a given state, on which it is possible to project the spin texture and its components. Finally, it is also able to plot the density of states (DOS), including the DOS projected by atoms (l-DOS) or orbitals (p-DOS), in addition to calculating the average value of the Charge Density, the Electrostatic Potential, and the Dielectric Function.

The code was written in simple language so that users without great knowledge of Python but with a basic understanding of programming logic can easily understand how it works and make their own modifications. The code is quite versatile in its construction, emphasizing the automation of tasks by minimizing user interaction. However, it optionally provides a series of customizations in the way the result is generated, including a small python code together with the output files, so that the user can make any changes he wants so that he is not limited only to the initial result provided by the code.

The main purpose of this article is to provide an overview of the code structure, in addition to demonstrating the program's different capabilities through illustrative examples. The program can run on Linux, Windows and MacOS platforms. The source code, tutorials, and examples are available in the PyPi [15], GitHub [16] and Zenodo [17] repositories. VASProcar will continue to be in continuous development, with increasing functionality, and due to the way the code was built it can be easily adapted to include the outputs of other DFT packages, such as Quantum Espresso, SIESTA, ABINIT, and WIEN2k. The remainder of this article is organized as follows: In Section 2 we briefly explain some basic aspects of VASProcar, in Section 3 we describe the post-processing features of the code, in Section 4 we use some example materials to illustrate the features described in section 3. Finally, we close with a summary in section 5.

2. Program Overview

2.1. VASProcar Design

The run of VASProcar is carried out by a set of internal codes, where each one has specific functions conditioned to the task requested by the user, which can be grouped into the following categories: **VASProcar interface**, **post-processing codes**, **codes for extracting data**, and **plotting codes**. The internal functioning structure of the code is described below and schematized in Fig. 1.

- I-II) The initial communication between the user and the VASProcar takes place through an interactive interface, from which the post-processing task is selected, starting the run of the corresponding code. If necessary, the interface continues to interact with the user, until all the specifics of the calculation have been duly informed. VASProcar minimizes interaction as much as possible, however, if the user is interested, a series of parameters can be inserted in order to obtain a personalized and more comprehensive calculation.
- III-IV) During the run of the post-processing, the information contained in the raw data of the DFT calculation is imported through of a series of extraction codes. The data set obtained is then properly organized and stored, both in memory through constants, vectors, and matrices, as on disk by writing temporary files.
- V-VI) After extracting the information from the DFT calculation, the post-processing is concluded with the analysis of the data set and the subsequent run of the corresponding plotting code, which provides a high-quality graphical representation, from which the user can properly interpret the results of his DFT calculation.
- VII) All VASProcar output files are stored in the “output” folder, created in the same directory where the analyzed DFT calculation files are located.

VASProcar is built to be very flexible since the implementation of new DFT packages can be done by adapting the extraction codes. Once the DFT calculation data is correctly imported, the rest of the VASProcar code is executed in exactly the same way, regardless of the DFT package used.

Figure 1: A structural overview of the VASProcar code.

2.2. VASP Package

The VASP (Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package) [3, 4, 5] is a software package used to calculate the electronic structure and molecular dynamics of materials at the atomic scale from first principles, by obtaining an approximate solution of the many-body Schrödinger equation, either within the density functional theory (DFT) [1, 2] by solving the Kohn-Sham equations [2], within the Hartree-Fock (HF) approximation through the Roothaan equations, or through a mixed approach using hybrid functionals. In VASP, the electron orbitals, electronic charge density, and local potential are expressed in sets of plane wave basis, with the interactions between electrons and ions described by pseudopotentials conserving norm or ultrasoft, or by projector-augmented-wave method (PAW) [18, 19].

2.2.1. PROCAR File

The PROCAR file of the VASP package stores the character of the orbital projection per ion of each band n at each of the k -points of the DFT calculation, obtained by projecting the Kohn-Sham wave functions $\phi_{n,k}$ into spherical harmonics $Y_{l,m}^\alpha$ centered at ion index α with orbital angular momentum l and magnetic quantum number m , that is, $|\langle Y_{l,m}^\alpha | \phi_{n,k} \rangle|^2$ [5]. Other information contained in the PROCAR file is the numbers of k -points, bands, and ions, the direct coordinates (k_1, k_2, k_3) in the first Brillouin zone, and the weight of each k -point used in numerical integration, as well as the energy value and occupation of each state. For a DFT calculation containing n_k k -points, n_b bands and n_i ions, the internal structure of the PROCAR file is provided by the following loop:

```
Loop in range nk
  Loop in range nb
    Loop in range ni
```

Below, we have the initial lines of an example PROCAR file, illustrating the initial step of the loop above.

```
PROCAR lm decomposed + phase
# of k-points: 500          # of bands: 32          # of ions: 2

k-point 1 : 0.00000000 0.00000000 0.00000000      weight = 0.00200000

band 1 # energy -9.60827189 # occ. 1.00000000

ion  s   py   pz   px   dxy  dyz  dz2  dxz  dx2  tot
 1  0.114 0.010 0.010 0.010 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.143
 2  0.585 0.001 0.001 0.001 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.587
tot  0.700 0.010 0.010 0.010 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.730
```

For spin-polarized (ISPIN = 2) or non-collinear (LNONCOLLINEAR = .TRUE.) calculation, after the orbital projection per ion, three additional projections will be written, referring respectively to the spin components in the directions x|y|z. In the case of the calculation with spin polarization, the PROCAR is split into two sets of projections, the first one contains the spin-up channel, while the second the spin-down channel.

```
 1 -0.011 -0.001 -0.001 -0.001 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.014
 2 -0.056 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.057
tot -0.068 -0.001 -0.001 -0.001 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.071
 1 -0.089 -0.008 -0.007 -0.007 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.111
 2 -0.455 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.456
tot -0.544 -0.008 -0.008 -0.008 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.567
 1 -0.071 -0.006 -0.006 -0.006 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.089
 2 -0.364 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.365
tot -0.435 -0.006 -0.006 -0.006 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 -0.454
```

For calculations using the parameter LORBIT = 12, an additional block is written containing the phase factors of the wave function (real and complex parts of the projection of the Kohn-Sham orbitals onto the atomic orbitals), it is advised to use these phases as a qualitative measure of projection [5].

ion	s	py	pz	px	dxy	dyz	dz2	dxz	dx2
1	0.156	0.503	0.101	0.083	0.034	0.001	0.004	0.011	0.003
1	-0.203	0.474	0.072	0.093	0.037	0.003	0.004	0.013	0.003
2	0.505	0.138	0.270	0.366	0.011	0.067	0.036	0.033	0.002
2	-0.548	0.133	0.265	0.363	0.013	0.069	0.036	0.035	0.002

2.3. Installation and Execution

VASProcar is supported by Python 3. The latest version of VASProcar, version 1.1.15.6 at the time of writing this article, can be installed using the Python Packaging Index (pip) via the command:

```
pip install vasprocar==1.1.15.6
```

During the installation via pip, the following Python modules (numpy [20], scipy [21], matplotlib [22], plotly [23], moviepy [24], and kaleido [25]) required by VASProcar are installed automatically. Alternatively, the installation of VASProcar can be performed using the source code present in the PyPI [15], GitHub [16] and Zenodo [17] repositories, along with a usage tutorial and examples illustrating its capabilities (including VASP input and output files). In this case, the installation of the modules can be performed through the VASProcar interactive interface or manually by the user through the command:

```
pip install <package_name>
```

For the code to run, the user must use the command below in the directory containing the VASP output files.

```
python3 -m vasprocar
```

The vast majority of VASProcar features require the PROCAR, OUTCAR, and CONTCAR output files, additionally the KPOINTS, DOSCAR, LOCPOT, PARCHG, and vasprun.xml files can be requested depending on the task requested by the user.

3. VASProcar Features

3.1. Band Structure

The band structure describes the energy levels accessible to electrons in reciprocal space, obtained by investigating the wave functions in a periodic array of atoms or molecules. It has been successfully used to explain the physics involved in different types of materials (insulators, semiconductors, and metals), as well as to describe their properties, such as optical absorption and emission processes, resistivity, and electrical conductivity, among others. The band structure of a material has an energy dispersion whose dimension is given by the periodicity of the lattice. Thus, systems confined in two dimensions such as nanoribbons or nanowires have a one-dimensional dispersion associated with the periodic direction of the system. A 2D plot (Energy E x path- k) is capable of providing complete information about its electronic structure. However, in two-dimensional systems such as monolayers or stacks, or three-dimensional systems such as the bulk of various materials, the 2D plot represents incomplete information about the system, as it does not accurately represent the shape of the Fermi surface, the behavior of spin texture along a plane or volume of the BZ, or be inefficient in searching for Weyl points. Therefore, graphical representations in the form of 3D plots, isosurfaces, 2D Fermi surfaces, or contour lines are necessary to adequately describe the energy dispersion of the states.

3.1.1. 2D Plot

The 2D plot of the band structure is the simplest and most commonly used graphical representation to describe the energy dispersion of a material, corresponding to a graph of the energy E of the states against the path- k traveled in the 1st BZ. Generally, the path- k corresponds to high-symmetry lines connecting points of interest, such as the Γ -point common to any crystal lattice, the K-point important in hexagonal systems such as graphene, or the TRIMs (time-reversal invariant momentum) important in the analysis of topological materials, as illustrated in Figures 2b, 5a, and 9a. The 2D plot attempts to capture the basic behavior of the band structure, using a reduced number of k -points and consequently requiring low computational power to obtain it. As examples, we have the 2D plots presented in Figures 2c, 5b-c, and 9c.

3.1.2. 3D Plot

The 3D plot is useful for analyzing how the energy dispersion behaves along a k -plane of the BZ, obtained by sweeping a certain mesh of k -points and corresponding to a graph of the energy E of the states against the pair of coordinates (k_i, k_j) cartesian $(i, j = x, y, z)$ or direct $(i, j = 1, 2, 3)$ coordinates. By comparing the 2D band structure plots of the PbSe stacking shown in Figures 5–6 with the 3D plot in Figure 7a, it is evident how the 3D plot encompasses a greater amount of information than would be possible with a large number of 2D plots scanning different directions. For the visualization of the 3D plot, VASProcar provides a 3D object output file in .html format viewed via a web browser, which can be easily manipulated by the user and allows the visualization of all possible directions of the band structure in the k -plane. Finally, the 3D object can also be shared and viewed without the need for the presence of VASProcar.

3.1.3. Isosurface

In certain situations, it is desirable to investigate the behavior of states over a volume of the BZ, such as in the search for Weyl points, which often occur at points- k outside of high-symmetry lines or planes, making their location difficult. In this type of situation, it becomes useful to graphically represent this information through a 3D plot with axes given by the cartesian $(i, j, l = x, y, z)$ or direct $(i, j, l = 1, 2, 3)$ coordinates, while the different energy values are represented by a set of isosurfaces. VASProcar performs this type of plot in order to represent both the energy dispersion of a state and the energy difference (in modulus) between a pair of states selected by the user.

3.1.4. 2D Fermi Surface

Just like in the 3D band structure plot, as seen in subsection 3.1.2, the 2D Fermi surface plot allows for the analysis of the band structure behavior along a given plane- k of the BZ. However, instead of generating a 3D plot scanning a certain energy range, a 2D projection is made for a specific energy value, that is, a 2D plot of the energy contour of the states. VASProcar allows, in a single calculation, to obtain the 2D Fermi surfaces for distinct energy values, as well as to gather the information from the different Fermi surfaces in a video file in the .mp4 format, in order to facilitate the visualization of the behavior of the Fermi surface as a function of energy.

3.1.5. Contour Levels

The 2D contour plot is similar to the 2D Fermi surface plot, as seen in subsection 3.1.4, except that only a single band is analyzed for a specific energy value. It is useful for tracking the energy dispersion behavior of a state along the k -plane as a function of energy.

3.2. Projections

In addition to simple band structure plotting, VASProcar has the ability to project various information onto the bands, such as the orbital and atom contributions, or a combination of these composing the character or spatial projection of the states, in order to provide a graphical representation of high-quality illustrating the details of the electronic structure of the system. The projection is performed for each band and k -point, by inserting spheres whose color denotes certain information and whose area corresponds to the relative magnitude.

3.2.1. Orbital Projection

The orbital projection allows identifying which orbital (or combinations of orbitals) effectively contribute to a given electronic state. The user can still restrict his analysis to a certain atom (or set of atoms) being useful in obtaining and interpreting the physics of the system, for example, identifying the states' character (see the section 3.2.3). VASProcar automatically identifies which type of calculation was performed (parameter LORBIT used) and which orbitals are written in the PROCAR file, according to table 1. All orbitals are automatically analyzed, leaving it up to the user to choose the output file that suits him best.

LORBIT	Orbitals
0, 5, 10	$S P D F$
1, 2, 11-14	$s p_y p_z p_x d_{xy} d_{yz} d_{z^2} d_{xz} d_{x^2-y^2} f_{y(3x^2-y^2)} f_{xyz} f_{yz^2} f_{z^3} f_{xz^2} f_{z(x^2-y^2)} f_{x(x^2-3y^2)}$

Table 1: Orbitals written in the PROCAR file as a function of the LORBIT parameter used in the DFT calculation, the presence of f -type orbitals is conditioned to the electronic distribution of the atoms as well as to the pseudopotentials used.

3.2.2. Spatial Projection

The spatial projection on the band structure provides information about which atoms or regions of the material effectively contribute to a given electronic state. For example, it is possible to estimate which atoms preferably contribute to the valence and conduction bands in the vicinity of the energy GAP, or else, in the confinement of topological materials, in order to verify the location on the surface of the states that occur within the GAP of the Bulk states.

3.2.3. Projection of the States' Character

Each electronic state is characterized at a given k -point by a certain character, which represents the combination of atomic orbitals that effectively contribute to the state. Generally, the character is maintained over several k -points of the ZB by gradually changing. This physical information can be useful in several cases, for example, assisting in the visualization of the inversion of bands that characterize the topological materials (exemplified in the section 4.2), or it can even help in the determination by group theory of the irreducible representations (IRREPs) of the states, from which it is possible to build an effective model via the k.p method or the method of invariants, as performed in a previous work [26]. VASProcar allows you to project different characters on the band structure (exemplified in the section 4.2), each one being specified by the user through a range of ions and their respective orbitals. Identification of the character of a given state can be done by inspecting the projections described in sections 3.2.1, 3.2.2, and 3.2.4.

3.2.4. Orbital and Atomic Contribution in the States (Table)

Alternatively, VASProcar allows printing the percentage contribution values of atoms and orbitals for a specific set of bands and k -points user-selected, in a structured text file similar to a table. This type of representation provides quantitative data, unlike projections onto the band structure that provide visual and qualitative information.

3.3. Projection of DOS (Density of States)

The density of states (DOS) provides information about the availability of states at each electronic level, whose magnitude is proportional to the number of states per energy interval in each level available to be occupied by electrons. VASProcar performs a 2D plot of Energy (eV) versus DOS, as well as the projections of the DOS onto the orbitals (projected DOS - pDOS), onto the ions of the lattice (local DOS - lDOS), or a combination of these two projections (projected and local DOS - plDOS), as exemplified in figures 2(e) and 4.

3.4. Projection of Spin

For non-collinear calculations (LNONCOLLINEAR = .TRUE.), VASProcar separately analyzes the spin components S_x | S_y | S_z (\uparrow , \downarrow) by projecting them onto different types of band structure plots (2D Plot, 3D Plot, Isosurface, 2D Fermi Surface, and Contour Levels - see the section 3.1). Additionally, for a given state, VASProcar is capable of generating a 2D plot of the spin vector $S_i S_j$ ($i, j = x, y, z$) on a plane- k of the BZ, as exemplified in figure 8, or a 3D plot of the spin vector $S_x S_y S_z$ over a given volume of the BZ. Meanwhile, for collinear calculations (LNONCOLLINEAR = .FALSE.) with spin polarization (ISPIN = 2), VASProcar highlights the spin channels (\uparrow , \downarrow) in the 2D plots of the band structure and density of states.

3.5. Other Features

3.5.1. Partial Charge Density

For calculations with the LPARD, LSEPB, and LSEPK parameters set to .TRUE., VASP is able to generate a partial charge density decomposed by band and k -point selected, recording this information in PARCHG files. The partial charge density (decomposed by band) is obtained by summing the local density of states (IDOS) for the eigenvalues of the analyzed band, corresponding to the modulus of the eigenstate. VASProcar is able to read the PARCHG file and generate a 2D graphical representation of its average value in the x | y | z directions as a function of the unit cell extension so that it is possible to associate the magnitude of the partial charge density along a certain direction and region of the lattice.

3.5.2. Electrostatic Potential

For calculations with the parameter LVTOT = .TRUE., VASP stores in the output file LOCPOT, the local electrostatic potential $V_{LOCPOT}(\mathbf{r})$. VASProcar is capable of reading the LOCPOT file and generating a 2D graphical representation of the average value of $V_{LOCPOT}(\mathbf{r})$ in the x | y | z directions as a function of the unit cell extension, in order to associate the magnitude of the electrostatic potential along a particular direction and region of the lattice. Through this information, it is possible, for example, to evaluate the work function of a material by investigating the behavior of $V_{LOCPOT}(\mathbf{r})$ along the confinement direction. The local electrostatic potential is given by the expression.

$$V_{LOCAL}(\mathbf{r}) = V(\mathbf{r}) + \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}' + V_{XC}(\mathbf{r})$$

Where $V(\mathbf{r})$ is the ionic potential, the second term in the expression above corresponds to the Hartree potential, while $V_{XC}(\mathbf{r})$ is the potential term for exchange and correlation.

3.5.3. KPOINTS Generator (2D and 3D Mesh)

VASProcar is capable of generating a KPOINTS file by scanning a given area in a plane or a given volume in the Brillouin zone. The corresponding 2D or 3D mesh can be built around a certain k-point of interest or else delimiting the upper and lower limits of each of the cartesian (k_x, k_y, k_z) or direct coordinates (k_1, k_2, k_3) . The usefulness of this KPOINTS occurs in calculations where the behavior of the energy dispersion or the spin texture must be analyzed along a certain region of the Brillouin zone. As examples, we can cite the visualization of the 3D Dirac cone of the Graphene monolayer, the search for contact points between the valence and conduction bands in a Weyl semimetal, and the visualization of the helicity of the spin texture of a topological material. Calculations using this KPOINTS file type can be used to generate 2D and 3D plots, construction of isosurfaces, 2D and 3D Fermi surfaces, as well as contour levels.

3.5.4. VASP Output Files Correction

Some VASP output files, such as **PROCAR**, **DOSCAR**, **OUTCAR** and **PARCHG**, may sometimes contain some writing errors, arising from the FORTRAN program language in which the VASP is compiled. Among the most common errors, we can mention the lack of space before a direct coordinate with a negative value, or the absence of the letter "e" to denote decimal places with more than 3 digits. In the examples below, on the left we see how information is often incorrectly written, while on the right we have the correct way they should have been written:

```
0.50000000-0.50000000 >> 0.50000000 -0.50000000
0.12345000-123 >> 0.12345000e-123
0.86000000-209 >> 0.86000000e-209
```

This type of error consequently can lead to an error or failure in the reading and interpretation of the DFT calculation data. VASProcar has lines of code that automatically detect these errors and make the necessary corrections, not requiring any type of correction in the VASP output files. However, there are other packages where this type of correction is necessary, for this reason, we have implemented in VASProcar the user's option to check and correct these files, making the substitutions exemplified above.

3.5.5. Merging Multiple Calculations

In certain situations, the calculation of the electronic structure can become computationally demanding or even impractical in the available hardware, for example, in the study of confined systems such as nanoribbons and layer stacking, where the number of atoms in the lattice becomes too large. Forcing the user to decrease the calculation parameters, such as cut-off energy, Brillouin zone sampling, or more commonly the number of k-points in the calculation of the band structure, causing loss of information and/or calculation precision. One of the solutions is to divide the calculation into several stages, where each one analyzes a certain part of the route over the ZB, for example, a calculation along the Γ -K-M- Γ path can be divided into three separate calculations, analyzing respectively the Γ -K, K-M and M- Γ paths. However, the analysis from the output files turns out to be more complex, since the information is now distributed among several files.

Thinking about this problem, VASProcar was configured in a way to read, naturally and automatically, the PROCAR files from different stages of the divided calculation. The only actions the user must take is to ensure before the DFT calculation that the final k-point of one calculation is the starting k-point of the next calculation, that all steps have exactly the same number of k-points and at the end of the calculation it must sequentially rename the different PROCAR files, as follows:

```
PROCAR.1 PROCAR.2 PROCAR.3 PROCAR.4 . . .
```

VASProcar automatically detects the total number of steps in the divided calculation and internally merges the information, making the necessary adjustments, such as the alignment of energies and the correct sequencing of k-points.

4. Examples

In this section, we use two sample materials to illustrate the post-processing capabilities of the VASProcar code, giving special attention to Lead Selenide (PbSe) through a close analysis of its electronic structure. The figures referring to the output of the VASProcar code contained in this section, do not have any editing in relation to their graphic elements, with the exception of small adjustments in the font size, or the insertion of some text/frame/arrow highlight.

4.1. DFT Calculations Parameters

The first principles calculations are performed using the density functional theory (DFT) [1, 2] within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) for the exchange and correlation functional, employing the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) parametrization [27]. Fully relativistic j -dependent pseudopotential, within the projector augmented wave method [18, 19], was used in the non-collinear spin-DFT formalism self-consistently. We use the Vienna *ab initio* Simulation Package (VASP) [3, 4, 5], with a plane waves base configured with a given cut-off energy and the Brillouin zone sampled with a number of k -points (Monkhorst-Pack grid) so that the total energy converged within the meV scale (see Table 2). The vacuum space in two-dimensional materials was set to 15 Å and atomic structures were optimized with a criterion that requires the force on each atom being less than 0.01 eV/Å. To accurately describe the relativistic effect, we include the spin-orbit coupling term (SOC) in our calculations.

Material	cut-off energy	BZ sample	lattice parameter (a)
PbSe* Bulk	500 eV	15x15x15	4.2497 Å
PbSe* Stacking	500 eV	9x9x1	4.2497 Å
Graphene Monolayer	400 eV	15x15x1	1.4243 Å

Table 2: Parameters used in DFT calculations: cut-off energy for the expansion in plane waves, number of k -points taken for sampling the Brillouin zone using the Monkhorst-Pack technique, and lattice parameter a taken unambiguously as the smallest separation distance between atoms of the same type. * PbSe under pressure

4.2. TCI 3D - PbSe Under Pressure

Lead Selenide (PbSe) is an IV-VI compound with a face-centered cubic (FCC) crystal lattice of the rock-salt type (figure 2a), presenting a small indirect energy gap around the points L of your 1^o Brillouin zone (figure 2b-c) [28]. In the two-dimensional limit of a monolayer, PbSe belongs to the class of two-dimensional topological crystalline insulators (2D TCI) [29, 30], while the 3D bulk of the material remains with a trivial topology since the SO coupling does not have the necessary magnitude to invert the character of the bands at the Fermi level, however, the application of pressure reinforces the relativistic effects, allowing the inversion of bands [31] and the consequent transition to the TCI 3D phase (figure 2g-h) [32]. In this section, we use VASProcar resources in order to carry out a detailed analysis of the electronic structure of PbSe in the 3D TCI phase, for this purpose we apply pressure to the pristine material by decreasing its lattice parameter (Pb-Pb/Se-Se distance) by about 3.2% from 4.3911Å to 4.2497Å.

In figure 2a we have the band structure of the bulk, where we verify that the energy gap at the Fermi level and around point L is maintained. In order to understand the physics involved in the valence and conduction bands, we performed respectively in the figures 2d-f the projection of the orbital contribution, the plot of the density of states, and the atomic projection, verifying a predominance of the orbitals S and P of Pb and Se atoms. This information is better described when we carry out the DOS projection by orbital (pDOS), by atoms (IDOS), or a combination of these (figure 4), or else in a more practical way when we print the table (figure 3) with the percentage of orbital/atomic contributions to the k -point and bands of interest. Through this information, we were able to characterize the valence and conduction bands through the following characters ($\phi_S^{Pb} + \phi_P^{Se}$) and ($\phi_P^{Pb} + \phi_S^{Se}$), which when projected onto the band structure of the calculus without (figure 2g) and with (figure 2h) SO coupling, evidences the band inversion characteristic of materials with non-trivial topology [33].

Figure 2: PbSe bulk under pressure: (a) Crystal lattice unit cell, (b) 1^o Brillouin zone, (c) Band structure, (d) Projection of orbitals, (e) Density of states, (f) projection of the Pb/Se contribution, and Projection of the character of states without (h) and with (i) SO.

```

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
K-point 250: Direct coord. (0.5, 0.5, 0.5)
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

Band 5
=====
Pb: ion 1  S = 38.54%  P = 0.00%  D = 3.87%  Px = 0.00%  Py = 0.00%  Pz = 0.00%  ...
Se: ion 2  S = 0.00%  P = 57.59%  D = 0.00%  Px = 19.20%  Py = 19.20%  Pz = 19.20%  ...
=====
Sum:      S = 38.54%  P = 57.59%  D = 3.87%  Px = 19.20%  Py = 19.20%  Pz = 19.20%  ...
=====

Band 6
=====
Pb: ion 1  S = 0.00%  P = 77.10%  D = 0.00%  Px = 25.70%  Py = 25.70%  Pz = 25.70%  ...
Se: ion 2  S = 19.76%  P = 0.00%  D = 3.15%  Px = 0.00%  Py = 0.00%  Pz = 0.00%  ...
=====
Sum:      S = 19.76%  P = 77.10%  D = 3.15%  Px = 25.70%  Py = 25.70%  Pz = 25.70%  ...
=====

```

Figure 3: Sample of the text file containing the percentage contribution of each orbital to each ion, for bands and k-points selected. Result referring to the calculation without SO of Bulk of PbSe under pressure.

Figure 4: Density of states of the PbSe Bulk under pressure: (a) total DOS, (b-c) Partial DOS projected onto Pb/Se atoms, (d-e) Partial DOS projected onto D/P orbitals, and (f-h) Partial DOS projected onto the Pb/Se P-orbitals and Pb D-orbitals.

Figure 5: (a) 2D projection of the Brillouin zone of PbSe confined in direction [001], band structure of the stacking of the PbSe under pressure without (b) and with (c) SO.

One of the main characteristics of topological materials is the arising of conducting boundary states, which are topologically protected against backscattering and originate within the GAP of the bulk states, due to the bulk-boundary correspondence at the interfaces of confined systems, such as the edges of a nanoribbon or surfaces of a stacking [33]. Here we investigate the surface states in a 44-layer stacking of PbSe under pressure, obtained by confining the bulk of the material in the [001] direction. We

assumed the surface to be the outermost 8 layers on both sides of the stacking, while the bulk was taken to be the innermost 28 layers. In figure 5 we have the band structure for the calculation without (b) and with (c) SO, while in figure 6(a) the spatial projection of the calculation with SO, which shows that the topological states are in fact located in the stacking surface and occur due to SO coupling. Here we must emphasize that these surface states do not occur in the pristine PbSe stacking since this material is a trivial insulator.

Figure 6: Projection of bulk and surface states (a) and spin textures on the upper (b) and lower (a) surface of the stacking of the PbSe under pressure.

Figure 7: 3D plot of the band structure of PbSe stacking under pressure (a) and Level Contours of the valence (b) and conduction (c) bands.

Non-trivial topology materials have been extensively researched in recent years for applications in spintronics, due to the presence of helical boundary states, which are protected from the unwanted dissipative effect of backscattering thanks to the presence of time-reversal symmetry and blocking spin-momentum, which fixes the spin orientation with respect to the propagation direction of the charge carrier in momentum space.

Figure 8: .

4.3. Graphene Monolayer

Graphene is a two-dimensional material composed of a planar monolayer, whose carbon atoms are organized in a hexagonal structure, resulting in one of the thinnest materials in existence [34, 35]. Its electronic structure at the Fermi level is characterized by the predominant presence of the orbital p_z forming bonds π out of the plane, resulting in electrons weakly bound to atoms and free to move around the crystal lattice or be excited to electronic levels with higher energies [35]. Consequently, this material has a Dirac-type linear energy dispersion without GAP and with high conductivity.

Here we use the example of Graphene, in order to demonstrate the ability of VASProcar to describe with high quality the energy dispersion, either of a particular state or of the entire band structure. In figure 9, we have respectively in (c) the 2D plot of the band structure, highlighting the linear crossing of the bands that occurs at the Fermi level and over the point K of its 1st ZB (see figure 9b), in (d) we performed a 3D plot of the valence and conduction bands, obtained by sweeping the plane $k_x k_y$ around point K with a grid of 140x140 points, showing the crossing at cone shape, since the linear dispersion occurs in all directions of the plane from point K, finally in (e) we have the 2D plot of the valence band level contours, composed of 15 contours of constant energy (Fermi surfaces 2D).

Figure 9: Graphene monolayer: (a) Crystal lattice unit cell, (b) 1^o Brillouin zone, and (c) Band structure, (d) 3D plot of band structure, and (e) Levels contour.

5. Summary

VASProcar is an open code written in the Python 3 language, structured in an easy-to-understand programming logic but at the same time very efficient for what it proposes, it has a friendly interactive interface whose main focus is to help researchers in the analysis of their DFT calculations. In this article, we provide an overview of the code's structure, demonstrate its capabilities by analyzing the electronic structure of different materials, highlight the extraction of information from the PROCAR output file of VASP, through which the plot of the band structure, as well as the projection of orbital and atomic contributions, of spin components and the character of the states, which can be performed in a very simple and automated way. VASProcar can be installed via the pip command, and its source code is available for download in the PyPi [15], GitHub [16] and Zenodo [17] repositories, along with a user manual and the input and output files of the examples present in this article. The release version of VASProcar supports the output files of the VASP package, but soon we intend to support the QE output files and in the future several other DFT packages. The code will remain in continuous development, with the addition of new functionalities as they become necessary, as an example, we intend to add the option of executing the code through a single input file, optionally dispensing with the use of the interactive interface, allowing that the code is used at the end of the DFT calculation and without direct user intervention, in queuing systems commonly present in clusters. We hope that VASProcar will become a useful toolkit supported by the scientific community, assisting researchers in electronic structure analysis and in their continuous search for new materials.

5.1. Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that may influence the work reported in this article.

5.2. Acknowledgements

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